

The Role of Latin in the Modern World

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Abstract: This article describes the role of Latin in the modern world, especially in medicine. Students study medical terms in Latin. First of all, the importance of correct reading and writing of Latin letters, understanding and memorization is widely highlighted grammar rules. The role of Latin in the formation of European languages and the enrichment of their professional expressions is expressed in huge size and diversity.

Keywords: medicine, Latin, medical terminology, terminology, Greek.

Latin remains an important cultural phenomenon of the modern era.

Although it is considered a "dead language", many areas of human activity are unthinkable without Latin. It serves as the main base language for European languages, Italian, Spanish, French, Portuguese, German, Romanian, Moldovan and others. Latin is mainly used by the modern Catholic Church as the official language, considering that the scope of Latin is very it is wide and has a great variety. Vatican documents are kept in Latin and papal messages are compiled.

According to the Western religious tradition, scientists are still writing dissertations in Latin, and even discussions are underway.

Latin plays an important role in medicine, anatomy and pharmacology.

Person All organs and body parts have Latin names or are Latinized. the names.

The same goes for the names of medicines; in this area , combining is especially important because without it there is no medicine - there will be movement in the vast sea of medicines. Recipes have long been written in Latin and according to certain rules, so in America , a written prescription should be easily understandable to all government medical professionals. Not only in America, but also in other countries , recipes are written in Latin. Latin is becoming a living language for medicine. Latin is the language of scientific communication for all doctors in the world. Consequently, medical terminology is included in the International Medical Dictionary of Latin and Greek Languages and their Forms. This glossary should be understandable at the same level for representatives of the medical sector all over the world. These dictionaries were written in both Latin and Greek the language.

The Greek words covered clinical terms and plants. Latin, as already mentioned, in the study of modern Romance languages languages are necessary because this is the history of languages, a lot of phonetic and grammatical terms, and it is possible to understand the peculiarities of vocabulary only on the basis of knowledge of Latin. Less is more Latin It also strongly influenced the grammatical and lexical system, which also applies to students of

Germanic languages (English, German and French). The Latin language will undoubtedly help in any field. During the formation of the French literary language, it was significantly influenced by the syntax of the Latin language, which influenced the rules of conjugation in French, as well as the forms of the infinitive. Latin is the basis of all modern languages.

Latin expressions are used in all aspects, not just in the field of medicine. Most of the roots of modern languages are derived from Latin words. Most of the manuscripts of European languages are based on the Latin alphabet. Latin terminology is firmly rooted in the fields of biology, chemistry, medicine and law.

Especially in the field of medicine, they are used Latin-Greek terms. Many words of wisdom expressed in Latin are wise expressions borrowed from the speech of ancient writers, philosophers and medical scientists. Such wise phrases of the Greek philosopher Hippocrates have come down to us as: *Ars longa, vita brevis* (life is short, art is eternal), *IN VIA est in Medicina via sine lingua Latina* (without Latin there is no way to medicine). There is no doubt about the need to study Latin in medical and veterinary institutes, at the faculties of biology and natural sciences of universities. Latin was used both for philosophical conversations and for everyday ones. Latin is used by the modern Catholic Church as the official language. Documents The Vatican is kept in Latin, and the papal epistles are summarized. According to the Western religious tradition, scientific dissertations and manuscripts are still written in Latin. Knowledge of Latin is indispensable for priests of the Catholic Church. In addition, European languages used Latin as a source of vocabulary enrichment. According to scientists, of the 20,000 most common words in the English language, about 10,400 are Latin, about 2,200 are Greek and only about 5,400 are Anglo-Saxon. Today, the total number of speakers of Romance languages is 580 million people. More than 60 countries use Romance languages as national or official languages (including: French -30, Spanish -20, Portuguese -7, Italian -3), and the Latin writing system is used about 30% of the time. The Latin language has a very clear system of word formation. Therefore, the Latin (and partly Greek) language serves to form scientific and technical terminology.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Latin, along with ancient Greek, still serves as a source of formation of international socio-political and scientific terminology. Obviously, learning Latin and maintaining a high level of knowledge in This area is an extremely urgent task of modern education. It is also worth noting that the Latin alphabet is also used directly when learning the language.

Every student entering a medical university is obliged and necessary first of all for a deep and perfect study of Latin because Latin is the language of medicine all over the world.

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